

**STUDIES IN SULPHANILAMIDES. PART XII. SOME DIANILS AND DIACYLS OF
ETHYLENE-BIS-N¹-SULPHANILAMIDE AND SOME N⁴-SULPHANIL-
AMIDO ALIPHATIC ESTERS***

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Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide has been reacted with aromatic aldehydes to give the dianils. Diacyl of ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide have been prepared by reacting it with the acid chlorides of aliphatic monocarboxylic acids. Sulphanilamide has been condensed with some aliphatic bromo-esters to give the N⁴-sulphanilamido esters which are hydrolysed to give the free acids.

Considering the encouraging bactericidal activity of anils of sulphanilamide and sulpha-pyridine (Kolloff, and Hunter, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 159, 1647; Grey *et al.*, *Biochem. J.*, 1937, 31, 724; Fournou *et al.*, *Compt. rend. soc. Biol.*, 1937, 205, 299) dianils of ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (Bami, Iyer and Guha, *Science & Culture*, 1945, 11, 269) of type A from (I) to (IX) have been prepared by heating the amine with 2 molecular proportions of different aldehydes at suitable temperatures without any solvent. The anils are light coloured powders insoluble in acid, alkali and usual organic solvents. They could not be crystallised and were purified by removing the starting materials. These compounds have sharp melting points and were obtained in good yields.

TYPE A.

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| (I) R = C ₆ H ₅ .CH- | (VI) R = α-(OH).C ₁₀ H ₇ .CH- |
| (II) R = m-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .CH- | (VII) R = C ₆ H ₅ .CH ₂ CH- |
| (III) R = α-(OH) C ₆ H ₄ .CH- | (VIII) R = C ₆ H ₅ .OH = CH.CH- |
| (IV) R = p-(OCH ₃) C ₆ H ₄ .CH- | (IX) R = C ₆ H ₅ O- |
| (V) R = 3-(OH)-4 (OCH ₃) C ₆ H ₃ .CH- | |

Miller *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1198) have reported that activity of straight chain aliphatic acyl derivatives of sulphanilamide increases with increase in the number of carbon atoms in acyl residues from C₂ to C₆, after which there is a sharp drop in activity. Bergman and Haskelberg (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1) suggested that increased fat solubility associated with lipophilic properties may be expected to be conferred on the resulting compound consequent to the introduction of fatty acid residues in the sulphanilamide molecule. With a view to conferring similar properties to ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (Bami *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) it has been reacted in pyridine solution with aliphatic acid chlorides having C₂ to C₆ carbon atoms, to form the corresponding diacyl derivatives of type B (I-VII). The products are usually insoluble in organic solvents and are purified by precipitation from their dilute alkali solutions with acid in the cold. White amorphous powder in good yields having sharp melting points are obtained.

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TYPE B.

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| (I) R = CH ₂ CO- | (V) R = (CH ₂) ₂ .CH.CH ₂ CO- |
| (II) R = CH ₂ .CH ₂ .CO- | (VI) R = CH ₂ .(CH ₂) ₄ .CO- |
| (III) R = CH ₂ .CH ₂ .CH ₂ .CO- | (VII) R = CH ₂ .(CH ₂) ₅ .CO- |
| (IV) R = (CH ₂) ₂ .CH.CO- | |

Streptosol (sulphanilylglycin), a soluble sulpha-drug has been reported to be therapeutically active (Kolloff, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 950; U. S. patent, 2142847). It was therefore considered worth while to prepare other similar N⁴-sulphanil-amido aliphatic esters and their corresponding free acid derivatives. N⁴-sulphanilamido-acetic ester and acid (F. P. 816988; B. P. 470462; Trefouel *et al.*, *Ann. Inst. Pasteur*, 1937, 58, 30) and N₄-sulphanilamidopropionic acid (Northey, *Chem. Rev.*, 1940, 27, 85) have already been reported in literature but no details are available. By reacting sulphanilamide with different aliphatic α-bromo esters in absolute alcohol compounds (I), (III), (V), (VII) and (IX) of type C have been obtained which on hydrolysis give (II), (IV), (VI), (VIII) and (X), respectively.

TYPE C.

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| (I) R = CH ₂ COOC ₂ H ₅ , | (VI) R = CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ COOH |
| (II) R = CH ₂ COOH | (VII) R = CH(COOC ₂ H ₅) ₂ |
| (III) R = CH ₂ CH ₂ COOC ₂ H ₅ , | (VIII) R = CH(COOH) ₂ |
| (IV) R = CH ₂ CH ₂ COOH | (IX) R = CH(C ₆ H ₅)COOC ₂ H ₅ |
| (V) R = CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ COOC ₂ H ₅ , | (X) R = CH(C ₆ H ₅)COOH |

EXPERIMENTAL.

Dianils of Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (Type A).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-benzylidene-sulphanilamide) (I).—Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (1.8 g.) and freshly distilled benzaldehyde (1 g.) were mixed together and heated for 4 hours at 150° in an oil-bath. The reactants formed a homogeneous mass and water drops collected on the cooler portions of the vessel. The product was stirred with hot alcohol and filtered, washed with alcohol till free of all unreacted benzaldehyde and was ground with dilute hydrochloric acid (3%, 15 c.c.). The acid-insoluble product was filtered, washed well with water and alcohol and finally dried as a white amorphous powder, m.p. 241-42°, yield 2.6g. (Found: N, 10.77. C₂₂H₂₆O₂N₂S₂ requires N, 10.25 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-m-nitrobenzylidene-sulphanilamide) (II).—Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (1.8 g.) and m-nitrobenzaldehyde (1.5 g.) were powdered together and heated at 100-120° for 2½ hours. The mixture melted and solidified into a light yellow solid. The product was isolated and purified as described in (I) as a light yellow powder, m.p. 211-12°, yield 3.1 g. (Found: N, 12.91. C₂₂H₂₁O₂N₂S₂ requires N, 13.23 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-o-hydroxybenzylidene-sulphanilamide) (III).—Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (1.8 g.) and salicylaldehyde (1.2 g.) were heated together for 2 hours at

135-145°. The product was worked up as in (I); m. p. 245°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: N, 9.42. $C_{22}H_{21}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 9.68 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-p-methoxybenzylidene-sulphanilamide) (IV).—Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (1 g.) and anisaldehyde (0.7 g.) were heated together for 2½ hours at 140-150°. A pasty mass was obtained which did not improve by stirring with alcohol or ether. This was kept in contact with water for 2 days when it solidified. The product was isolated and purified as in (I) as a white amorphous powder, m.p. 168-69°, yield 1.3 g. (Found: N, 8.90. $C_{26}H_{26}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 9.42 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-3-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzylidene-sulphanilamide) (V).—Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (1 g.) and vanillin (0.9 g.) were heated for 3 hours at 150°. The compound was isolated and purified from its crude pasty form as in (IV) as a light coloured powder, m.p. 237° (decomp.), yield 0.9 g. (Found: N, 8.25. $C_{30}H_{30}O_6N_4S_2$ requires N, 8.77 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-α-hydroxynaphthylidene-sulphanilamide) (VI).—Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (1 g.) and α-hydroxynaphthaldehyde (1.4 g.) were heated together for 2 hours at 130-140°. The product was isolated as under (I) in the form of a brownish yellow powder, m.p. 275-77°, yield 2 g. (Found: N, 8.33. $C_{26}H_{22}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 8.25 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-phenylacetylidene-sulphanilamide) (VII).—Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (1 g.) and phenylacetaldehyde (0.7 g.) were heated for 1¼ hours at 150°. The product obtained as under (I) was a light yellow powder, m.p. 133°, yield 1.3 g. (Found: N, 9.1. $C_{26}H_{26}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 9.75 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-cinnamylidene-sulphanilamide) (VIII).—Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (2 g.) and freshly distilled cinnamic aldehyde (1.5 g.) were heated together for 1¼ hours at 130°. The mixture was worked up as in (I) and the product obtained as a light brown powder, m.p. 172°, yield 2.8 g. (Found: N, 9.12. $C_{28}H_{26}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 9.36 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-furfuralidene-sulphanilamide) (IX).—Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (1.5 g.) and furfuraldehyde (2 c.c.) were heated together for 2 hours at 150°. The product was isolated as in (I) as a light coloured powder, m.p. 225°, yield 1.3 g. (Found: N, 10.34. $C_{24}H_{22}O_6N_4S_2$ requires N, 10.65 per cent).

Diacyls of Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (Type B).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-acetylsulphanilamide) (I).—Ethylene-bis-N¹-sulphanilamide (3.7 g.) was taken in dry pyridine (10 c.c.) and acetyl chloride (2 g.) was carefully added to it drop by drop. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 1 hour under anhydrous conditions. The mixture was diluted with water (15 c.c.) and hydrochloric acid (2 c.c., 10%), when the product came out as a semi-solid mass. The product was dissolved in minimum alkali solution (2%) and the alkali solution after stirring with charcoal was filtered and acidified in cold. The white precipitate was collected, washed well with water and alcohol and finally dried as a white amorphous powder, m. p. 275°, yield 4 g. (Found: N, 12.37. $C_{16}H_{22}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 12.33 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-propionyl-sulphanilamide) (II).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide (3.7 g.) and propionyl chloride (2 g.) were reacted together in pyridine and the product obtained as in (I) as a white amorphous powder, m.p. 271°, yield, 3.8 g. (Found: N, 11.41. $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 11.6 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-butyryl-sulphanilamide) (III).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide (3.6 g.) and butyryl chloride (2 g.) were reacted together and purified product obtained as in (I) as a white amorphous powder, m. p. 262-63°, yield 4 g. (Found: N, 10.52. $C_{22}H_{26}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 10.98 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-isobutyryl-sulphanilamide) (IV).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide (3.6 g.) and isobutyryl chloride (2 g.) were reacted and the product isolated as in (I). as a white amorphous powder, m. p. 256°, yield 3 g. (Found: N, 10.29. $C_{22}H_{26}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 10.98 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-isovaleryl-sulphanilamide) (V).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide (3.7 g.) was added to benzene (20 c. c.), and to this mixture isovaleryl chloride (2.4 g.) was added and the mixture refluxed for 6 hours on a water-bath under anhydrous conditions. The solid obtained was filtered and washed with ether and alcohol and finally obtained as a white amorphous powder after precipitating twice from its dilute alkali solution with acid in cold, and subsequent crystallisation from alcohol, m. p. 202°, yield 4.4 g. (Found: N, 10.0. $C_{21}H_{24}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 10.4 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-caproyl-sulphanilamide) (VI).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide (1.8 g.) and caproyl chloride (1.4 g.) were reacted together and the product obtained as in (V) as a light coloured amorphous powder, m. p. 206°, yield 1.2 g. (Found: N, 9.3. $C_{22}H_{28}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 9.89 per cent).

Ethylene-bis-N¹-(N⁴-heptoyl-sulphanilamide) (VII).—Ethylene-*bis-N¹*-sulphanilamide (1.8 g.) and heptoyl chloride (1.5 g.) were reacted in pyridine and the product obtained as in (V) as a light coloured powder m. p. 182°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 8.9. $C_{23}H_{28}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 9.42 per cent).

N⁴-Sulphanilamido-aliphatic Esters and Acids (Type C).

N⁴-Sulphanilamidoacetic Ester (I).—Sulphanilamide (7 g.), absolute alcohol (20 c. c.) and ethyl bromoacetate (4 g.) were refluxed together on a water-bath for 12 hours. Sulphanilamide gradually went into solution and afterwards, alcohol was distilled off and the semi-solid mass was stirred with alcohol-free ether and filtered. Ether-insoluble product was washed with a little more ether, dried and ground with hydrochloric acid (5%, 20 c.c.). The acid-insoluble product was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol after treating with charcoal (norit). The product was insoluble in other organic solvent and obtained as a white silky needles, m. p. 136-38°, yield 4.2 g. (Found: N, 10.7; S, 12.1. $C_{10}H_{11}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 10.8; S, 12.4 per cent).

N⁴-Sulphanilamidoacetic Acid (II).—*N⁴*-Sulphanilamidoacetic ester (4 g.) and potassium hydroxide solution (10%, 15 c.c.) were refluxed together for 4 hours. The solution was filtered and acidified with minimum hydrochloric acid (15%). The precipitated product was filtered, washed with water (2 c. c.) and crystallised from hot water after treating with charcoal (norit) as a white amorphous powder, m. p. 245° (decomp.), yield 2.8 g. (Found: N, 12.21. $C_7N_3O_4N_2S$ requires N, 12.1 per cent).